

Formation Studies on Ternary and Quaternary Complexes of some Lanthanides

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The formation of 1 : 1 : 1, Ln(III)-PDA-NTA/FA ternary complexes and 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, Ln(III)-PDA-NTA-FA quaternary complexes, where Ln(III) = La, Pr and Nd; PDA = pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid, NTA = nitrilotriacetic acid and FA = furan-2-carboxylic acid, has been studied potentiometrically. The formation constants for the resulting ternary and quaternary complexes have been evaluated at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) and temperature ($28 \pm 1^\circ$). The order of stability constants in terms of metal ions have been found both in ternary and quaternary complexes as $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III}$, and this order has been explained in terms of increased number of fused rings and coordination number of the metal ions.

Lanthanides due to their high electropositive character and hydrolytic nature have a little tendency to form complexes particularly with N and S donor ligands. Only few references¹ have been reported on their quaternary complexes in which these metal ions not only form stable complexes but also expand their coordination number beyond six².

In the present communication we report the pH-metric studies on 1 : 1 : 1, Ln(III)-PDA-NTA/FA ternary and 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, Ln(III)-PDA-NTA-FA quaternary complexes with an aim to compare their formation stabilities and effect on their coordination number.

Results and Discussion

Similar type of curves were obtained in the respective systems of all the three metal ions, hence for the sake of brevity, the curves for 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-PDA-NTA-FA have only been discussed to explain the formation of ternary and quaternary complexes.

A well-defined inflection on curve 'a' (Fig. 1) at $m \sim 2.5$ indicates the basic-salt formation³ of the metal which is in conformity with the earlier observations⁴ (m = moles of alkali added per mole of the metal ion or ligand). Similarly, a single inflection at $m = 2$ on curve 'b' represents the titration of two carboxylic protons present in pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid. Curve 'c' giving inflections at $m = 1$ and $m = 2$, depicts the titration of monopotassium salt of nitrilotriacetic acid. Curve

'd' attributes the titration of 2-furoic acid giving an inflection at $m = 1$, indicating the titration of carboxylic proton present in this acid.

Binary system : Curve 'e' (Fig. 1) illustrates the titration of 1 : 1, M(III)-PDA. An inflection at $m = 2$ may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1, M(III)-PDA binary complex. Another inflection at $m \sim 3.5$ may, however, be ascribed to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1 : 1, complex into 1 : 2, M(III)-PDA species and to the precipitation of the remaining metal as hydroxide. Curve 'f' depicts the titration of 1 : 1, M(III)-NTA. An inflection at $m = 2$ is due to formation of 1 : 1 M(III)-NTA complex⁵. Another inflection at $m = 3$ shows the addition of one more OH⁻ group to the initially formed complex.

Curve 'g' (Fig. 1) representing the titration of 1 : 1, M(III)-FA system gives an inflection at $m = 1$ which may be due to the formation of 1 : 1, M(III)-FA species. Another inflection at $m \sim 3$ followed by the precipitation may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 3, M(III)-FA complex and the simultaneous precipitation of metal hydroxide.

Fig. 1. *m* vs pH plots for 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-PDA-NTA-FA system : (a) La(NO₃)₃, (b) PDA, (c) NTA, (d) FA, (e) 1 : 1, La(III)-PDA, (f) 1:1, La(III)-NTA, (g) 1 : 1, La(III)-FA, (h) 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-PDA-NTA, (i) 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-PDA-FA, (j) 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-NTA-FA, (k) 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-PDA-NTA-FA, (T) theoretical composite curve and (→) appearance of ppt.

Ternary system : Curve 'h' (Fig. 1) representing the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-PDA-NTA species gives an inflection at *m* = 4 depicting the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, ternary complex in the lower pH range due to the titration of protons of PDA and two protons of NTA simultaneously,

Curve 'i' depicts the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-PDA-FA mixed system. An inflection at *m* = 3 indicates the complexation of metal ion with both the involved ligands simultaneously, which is further supported by the formation of a white precipitate at pH > 7.3.

A well-defined inflection on curve 'j' at *m* = 3 indicates the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-NTA-FA complex. Another inflection at *m* ~ 4.5 on this curve indicates the disproportionation of the initially formed ternary complex at higher pH according to the equation,

The above mechanism is further supported by the appearance of a precipitate at pH ≈ 8, which on isolation and testing did not give test for nitrogen qualitatively.

Quaternary systems : Curve 'k' (Fig. 1) depicts the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, M(III)-PDA-NTA-FA quaternary system. An initial lowering in pH as compared to the binary and ternary systems and a sharp inflection at *m* ~ 5 represents the simultaneous addition of all the three ligands to the metal ion forming 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, mixed ligand species,

TABLE 1-FORMATION CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 : 1, TERNARY AND 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, QUATERNARY COMPLEXES

Temp. = 28 ± 1°, μ = 0.1 M KNO₃, KOH = 0.1 M ; Concn. : M(III) = PDA = NTA = FA = 5.0 × 10⁻³ for PDA (L), pk₁ = 1.7 ± 0.07, pk₂ = 4.56 ± 0.06; for NTA (L'), pk = 2.63 ± 0.04; for FA (L''), pk = 3.36 ± 0.02

Metal ion M(III)	1:1:1, M(III)-PDA-NTA/FA system		1 : 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-PDA-NTA-FA system
	NTA	FA	
	log K _{MLL'}	log K _{MLL''}	log K _{MLL'L''}
La	4.04 ± 0.17	5.55 ± 0.11	7.70 ± 0.12
Pr	5.57 ± 0.08	6.04 ± 0.19	8.58 ± 0.11
Nd	6.28 ± 0.15	7.03 ± 0.16	9.22 ± 0.10

Formation constants of mixed-ligand species : The values of formation constants have been given in Table 1. The relative stabilities of the resulting ternary and quaternary species (log k_{MLL'}, log k_{MLL''})

and $\log K_{MLL'L'}$ respectively) in terms of metal ions have been observed to follow the order : $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III}$ which is in the conformation of the earlier observations^{6, 7} and may be explained on the basis of decreasing size and increasing ionic potential (charge/radius ratio) of lanthanides. In terms of complex species, the order quaternary > ternary may be explained on the basis of the increased number of fused rings⁸ and extra-stabilisation caused by ligand-ligand interactions in quaternary complexes. Since, there are five fused rings in 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-PDA-NTA complex, it should be more stable than the 1 : 1 : 1, M(III)-PDA-FA complex, which has only four fused rings. But the values of stability constants have been found in reverse order. This reverse order can be explained on the basis of coordination number of metal ions in these complexes. In 1 : 1 : 1 Ln(III)-PDA-FA complex, the metal ions attain its usual six-coordination number giving the stable octahedral geometry. Whereas, unusual coordination number 7 is revealed in 1 : 1 : 1, Ln(III)-PDA-NTA complex which affects its stability.

Experimental

Solutions of all the chemicals (AnalaR or G.R., E. Merck) were prepared in double-distilled water. Standard solutions of lanthanide nitrates were prepared and standardised by the usual methods⁹. Solutions of pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (PDA), nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and furan-2-carboxylic acid (FA) were prepared by direct weighing. The concentrations of the ligand and metal solutions were further checked by pH-metric titrations against 0.1 M KOH solution.

General procedure : The pH-metric titrations were carried out against 0.1 M KOH solution with a Toshniwal CL-46 pH-meter using a combined electrodes assembly at $28 \pm 1^\circ$ with the help of an electrically controlled thermostat. The instrument was standardised against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (pH = 4) in the beginning of each titration. The total volume (50 ml) and ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) of each system were kept constant in the beginning of each titration.

The dissociation constants of the ligands were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹⁰. The formation constants of the ternary

and quaternary complexes were calculated by the modified method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa³.

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